

PRINCIPALS' TIME MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND ADMINISTRATIVE EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EDO STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between principals' time management practices and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo state. Two research questions were raised to guide the study, one was answered, while one was hypothesised and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a descriptive survey based on a correlational design. The study population comprised 617 principals in public junior and senior secondary schools in Edo State. A stratified random sampling technique was used in the selection of 122 principals representing 20% of the population. Two sets of questionnaires were used to collect data for the study. The first instrument was titled: "Principals' Time Management Practices Questionnaire" (PTMPQ) while the second instrument was titled "Principals' Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire" (PAEQ). The content validity of the instruments was determined by the expert judgment of three experts in the Faculty of Education, University of Benin. The internal consistency reliability test was used to establish the reliability of the questionnaires and Cronbach alpha coefficients of 0.81 and 0.89 respectively were obtained. Data collected were analyzed using mean, percentage, frequency and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to determine a relationship. The findings revealed that the level of principals' administrative effectiveness was moderate. There was a significant relationship between principals' time management practices and level of administrative effectiveness. Based on these findings, it was concluded that proper time management is vital for the effective administration of schools.

Keywords: *principals, time management practices, administrative effectiveness, public secondary schools.*

Introduction

Principals as school administrators are expected to make effective use of existing humans and

other available resources at their disposal to realize school goals. However, experience has shown that resources including time required for effective school administration are usually limited in supply. The responsibilities of the principals and the attendant constraints in meeting the goals of the system exert unbearable demands at the time they have at their disposal. It is not surprising that for many principals the task of school administration seems a bit overwhelming. It requires the adoption of appropriate administrative practices by the principals to overcome the challenges of effective handling of administrative duties, such as how to effectively implement the curriculum, support teachers towards effective teaching and learning, effectively dealing with disciplinary issues, as well as dealing effectively with the provision and maintenance of school physical facilities among other issues. How principals attend to these tasks largely determines their effectiveness or otherwise as school administrators.

Ifedili (2002) is of the view that many public schools are ineffectively managed by principals. The administrative effectiveness of principals is believed to be a factor that facilitates attainment of secondary school goals. Principals' ineffectiveness in performing administrative tasks may result in problems such as examination malpractice, poor academic performance, indiscipline among staff and students as well as poor attitude of teachers to their jobs. Principals' consciousness and attitude towards tasks and time in the process of performing their duties can promote or hinder their effectiveness. The effectiveness of principals depends on the extent they perform their administrative functions effectively.

The time management practices that can enhance principals' effectiveness in school administration include planning for tasks, prioritizing activities, scheduling of tasks, punctuality and regularity to work, effective assignment of personnel duties, effective delegation, effective communication, effective meeting management as well as staff and students' personnel management, setting clear, realistic and measurable goals. In addition to the above, fostering good interpersonal relationships among staff, effective management of routine office duties and time schedules for school activities, setting and implementing reasonable deadlines, ensuring timely repairs and replacement of materials and equipment, and minimizing distractions are all essential time management practices for school administration.

Responding quickly to mails, memos, and reports, as well as using a good filing system, will help principals handle their time better. A good filing system improves record keeping, orderliness, and speed of retrieval of documents. For effective time management by principals, careful editing of letters and memos to ensure that they express the correct and intended information is necessary, as this will save time that would have been spent clarifying issues. Goals, operational procedures, and other relevant information must be communicated in a timely manner to avoid misunderstanding, since those in the school will not be aware of what to do at the appropriate time, thus causing the school's smooth operation to suffer. Before the start of a new school year, an effective principal is required to prepare and create an opening schedule. An effective principal thinks and plans, anticipates challenges, and prepares accordingly to deal with them.

Furthermore, being regular and punctual at work will help principals to model punctuality and regularity at work and motivate others to develop the same attitude to work. This will prevent piling of work and help them to be abreast of the happenings and practices in the school as well as giving the principals the moral integrity to discipline staff members who are not punctual and regular at school. Participatory management creates a sense of belonging, value and ownership which motivates commitment to common goal achievement. The practice where some principals unnecessarily distant themselves from their subordinates could cause work overload for the principals, thereby affecting their effectiveness. However, principals need to balance their time with the subordinates, as being too readily available or very unavailable has serious consequences that must be avoided. Effective delegation of duties will free

up some time for the principals to attend to other administrative duties and be available for consultation as well as create opportunities for the subordinates to learn on the job.

For effective school administration, a properly planned timetable is used to control school time. All school events are correctly arranged with adequate time and allocation of place. The principal is also responsible for supervising teaching activities to ensure that teachers adhere to the scheme of work, promptly and adequately plan for their lessons, and use the appropriate teaching methodology and instructional materials so that students acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. Teachers who do not strictly adhere to the time schedule for curricular and co-curricular activities will interrupt other school activities and make it more difficult to achieve goals. An effective principle ensures that students and teachers adhere to the school's activities schedule.

Prior to the beginning of a new term, he ensures that the school timetable is planned. All school events, such as opening and closing, lectures, break, examinations, labour and extra-curricular activities, are prioritized to maximize the use of school time. As a result, when conducting their duties, principals must be mindful of the time schedule to avoid disrupting scheduled school time. Some principals may be spending so much time on the activities they shouldn't spend much time doing. This portends poor time management by principals who are expected to effectively manage school time for effectiveness. Allocation of time by the principal to each task to be performed, such as teaching supervision, meetings, paperwork, and outside school duties, may improve their time management and administrative effectiveness.

The effective and productive use of time is critical to achieving school goals. The effectiveness of a school administrator is assessed based on the desired outcome, how it is achieved, and the impact on others (Mullins 2007). To be effective, the principal must carry out his or her responsibilities in a timely and efficient way. However, inefficient use of resources within the time frame allotted could lead to products that aren't suitable for society's needs. To a large degree, how well they use the time they have at their disposal depends on how well they spend it on the right activity. As a result, the principals must be adept at making time-use decisions. There is no gain saying the fact that if principals are required to perform their mandated roles in schools, their effectiveness would begin not only with their task but also with their time. By efficiently managing school activities and time, principals reduce time waste. The way principals plan and spend time on their different tasks each day will influence their effectiveness to a large degree.

Administration is particularly important because it has such a large effect on the achievement of school programmes, priorities, and instructional goals (Peretemode, 2008). According to Chapman and Austin in Puvvada (2015), school administration is basically what principals do, and it is ensuring that the day-to-day school operations are performed efficiently and effectively. Effectiveness is not one-dimensional, but rather depends on the way that various resources work in combination. In the school system, it involves questions about whether school graduates are well prepared, whether they have the skills, knowledge and abilities that they and society demand because of their studies (Lunenborg & Ornstein, 2004).

Administrative effectiveness is described by Muraina (2014), as the achievement of a set of goals, using the appropriate quantity and quality of resources at the appropriate time and location. Effectiveness revolves around the achievement of goals. Administrative effectiveness is the product of the interaction of personal qualities and aspects of the principals' job in meeting the situation's requirements (Mullins, 2007). The criterion for evaluating a manager's effectiveness should be thought about in terms of the outcomes that the principal is expected to achieve. However, the manner in which the manager achieves results, as well as the consequences on others are equally important (Mullins, 2007). He stressed that principals are likely to be judged not just on their own accomplishments, but also

on the performance of other staff.

The principal's effectiveness can be measured by a variety of factors, including time management, meeting critical deadlines, staff motivation and productivity, training and growth performance, and the establishment of an operational atmosphere in which staff and students work willingly and effectively, as well as commitment to quality standards. If a school achieves specific goals, it is said to be effective. Thus, administrative effectiveness indicates how well an administrator fulfills the requirements of his or her role in an organization. The goal of all principals' activities is bringing students to their highest standard of performance. This supports McCrimmon's (2007) assertion that schools are not effective in any sense unless the principals are effective. In school systems in particular, waste results from the inefficient utilization of resources within the available time frame, and such waste manifests itself in the irrelevance or inappropriateness of the products to the needs of the system's environment (Kalu, 2012).

According to Mullins (2007), it is a complex phenomenon to describe and measure, since effectiveness is a concept reflecting the values and biases of the individual rating. Thus, the most common criterion for rating according to Hallinger and Heck (1996) is observable behaviour in specific situations in relation to the expectation of the individual rating. Due to differing expectations, a person considered ineffective in each situation by one person could be rated effective by another.

Researchers have examined several possible connections to better understand the relationship between time management and administrative effectiveness. According to Shipman (1997), principals' administration and time management issues are strongly linked to school performance. Ogonor and Imarhiagbe (2007) investigated effectiveness of principals in the performance of school tasks in Edo State, Nigeria. A research question and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all the teachers in the secondary schools in Edo State. The sample size for the study was 2991 teachers selected using the simple random sampling technique. An instrument titled: "Principals Effectiveness in the Performance of School Task Questionnaire" (PEPSTQ) was used to collect data. Face and content validity of the instrument were ensured. The Cronbach alpha reliability estimate of PEPSTQ was given as 0.87 which guaranteed the use of the instrument for the study. Mean and t-test of two independent means were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The findings revealed that principals in Edo State are effective in the performance of administrative functions, though school principals varied significantly in the management of school functions based on school size and school location.

Adebayo and Omojola, (2012) examined the impact of time management on administrative effectiveness in higher education institutions in Ekiti State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a survey based on correlational research design. The population of the study comprised all the administrators, academic and non-academic staff in higher education institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 150 administrators, 300 academic and non-academic staff selected using the simple random sampling technique. Two self-constructed instruments titled: "Time Management Impact Questionnaire" (TMIQ) and "Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire" (AEQ) were used to collect data. Face and content validity of the instruments were ensured. The Cronbach alpha reliability estimates of TMIQ and AEQ were given as 0.80 and 0.72 respectively which guaranteed the use of the instruments for the study. Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The findings revealed that time management influences administrative effectiveness in higher education institutions. This finding may be since proper time management ensures that all tasks are efficiently and timely performed to guarantee excellence and effectiveness.

Ekundayo and Kolawole (2013), examined the time management skills and administrative effectiveness of principals of secondary schools. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all the principals in Ondo, Ekiti and Osun State. The sample size for the study was 200 principals and 600 teachers selected using the simple random sampling technique. A questionnaire titled: "Principals' Time Management Skills and Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire" (PTMSAEQ) was used to collect data. Face and content validity of the instrument was ensured. The Cronbach alpha reliability estimate of PTMSAEQ was given as 0.74 which guaranteed the use of the instrument for the study. Frequency counts, Percentage, Mean, and Standard Deviation were used to analyze the data collected and all the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The findings revealed that the level of administrative effectiveness was encouraging and there was a relationship between time management skills and administrative effectiveness of principals. This indicates that principals effectively carry out their managerial duties to create an enabling environment for others in the school to perform optimally.

Time spent by principals on certain instruction-related activities, such as counseling and teacher professional development, is linked to better student performance (Grissom, *et al* 2016).

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that effective school administration rests on time management abilities of the principal. Some principals also tend to spend a long-time addressing student during morning assembly, an activity that should not exceed 10 minutes. Principals, it seems, tend to carry out administrative tasks without proper planning thus focusing on some tasks while neglecting other critical tasks. This appears to have resulted in indiscipline among members of the school community. This indiscipline can be expressed in absenteeism and lateness to school and classes by staff and students, non-compliance with scheduled school timetable for activities, unauthorized movement from school by staff and students, teachers teaching without adequately planned lesson plans and notes and other forms of indiscipline which appears to be indices of poor school administration. This could result in students not acquiring the desired skills, knowledge and attitude required for higher education and useful living within society. The researchers are worried that some principals who have been entrusted with the important task of school administration do not seem able to manage their time effectively.

The pertinent question that arises is: Can the time management practices of principals guarantee administrative effectiveness? Therefore, this study sought to find out if there is any relationship between time management practices and administrative effectiveness of principals in public secondary schools in Edo state.

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on Stephen Covey's Time Quadrants model, developed in 1994, and Reddin's 3-Dimension theory of managerial effectiveness, propounded in 1970. According to the time quadrant model, organizing tasks based on importance and urgency will help in identifying important and urgent tasks that require focus and attention for goal achievement. This will prevent wasting time on things that aren't necessary and won't help in achieving goals.

Effectiveness is contingent upon the appropriateness of the principal's behaviour with the situational demands. How school principals behave in any situation is influenced by their value system. And nothing says more about one's priorities and values than how one allocates and spends time. The behavioural style of management adopted towards staff and tasks may be determined by perceptions about people, human nature and work (Mullins, 2007). Development of a cordial and supportive relationship creates a school climate conducive to realization of school goals.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey based on correlational research design. The population of the study comprised all the six hundred and seventeen (617) principals of Public Junior and Senior Secondary Schools in Edo State. The sample size for this study was 122 principals representing 20% of the population of principals. The stratified random sampling technique was used to select the principals for the study. 20% of samples were selected randomly from the 18 local government areas based on their relative number in the population. There were 3,989 teachers in the public secondary schools in Edo state. Four (4) teachers in each of the schools of the sampled principals were randomly selected to rate their principals' administrative effectiveness.

The instrument for data collection for this study were two questionnaires designed by the researcher titled "Principals' Time Management Practices Questionnaire" (PTMPQ) and "Principals Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire" (PAEQ). The principals in the sampled schools were expected to respond to the first instrument while the teachers in the sampled schools were to respond to the second instrument. The PTMP questionnaire was in three sections; A, B, and C. Section A consisted of 5 items which elicited demographic information. Section B comprised 20 items that elicited information on principals' management practices. The four-point Likert scale based on Always (4), Often (3), Sometimes (2) and Never (1) was used in response to the statements on the questionnaire. Section C was a checklist that sought how much time principals spent on sixteen (16) administrative tasks. The principals' schedule for administrative activities was indicated as 1 to 15minutes, above 15-30 minutes, above 30 to 1 hour and above 1 hour.

The PAE questionnaire was in two sections; A and B. Section A consisted of 2 items which elicited demographic information. Section B comprised 36 items centered on the administrative functional areas of the principals and elicited information on the level of administrative effectiveness of the principals. The four-point Likert scale based on Highly Effective (4), Effective (3), Ineffective (2) and Highly Ineffective (1) was used in response to the statements on the questionnaire.

The validity of the instruments (questionnaires) was determined by three lecturers from the Faculty of Education, University of Benin. The experts made their comments and suggestions on the content validity of the instruments. Corrections made were effected in the drafting of the final instruments. The two instruments, which are Principals Time Management Practices Questionnaire (PTMPQ) and Principals Administrative Effectiveness Questionnaire (PAEQ) were administered to 60 respondents (30 principals and 30 teachers) that were not part of the study. The responses were analyzed using Cronbach alpha to determine the reliability of the two instruments. This yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81 for the PTMPQ and 0.90 for the PAEQ respectively. This indicated that both instruments were reliable.

The researcher and assistants administered the questionnaires and the completed copies of the questionnaires were retrieved immediately. This was done to guarantee a high rate of return. One hundred and twenty (120) of the administered instruments were returned completed, representing 98% percent return rate.

To answer research question 1, descriptive statistics of frequency, mean, standard deviation, and range of scores were used to analyze the data collected. Always (4), Often (3), Sometimes (2), and never (1) were the responses to each item on section B of the Principals' Time Management Practices (PTMP) questionnaire. Each principal's scores on the twenty (20) items were added together. The maximum total score for each principal was eighty (80) while the minimum score was twenty (20). The mean and standard deviation of the one hundred and twenty principals on each item was also obtained. The normative meaning was established by adding up the scores of the responses, $(4+3+2+1=10)$ divided by the highest score (4), $10/4=2.50$. Decision was reached using mean range value of 1-1.49 as never, 1.50-2.49 as sometimes, 2.50-3.49 as often while 3.50 and above as always. The time range was 1

to 15 minutes, above 15-30 minutes, above 30 minutes to 1 hour and above 1 hour. Research question 1, was analyzed using mean range values: 1-1.99 was regarded as low, 2.00-2.99 was regarded as moderate while 3.00-4.00 was regarded as high.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r) was used to determine relationships. The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1

What is the level of principals’ administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo State?

To answer this question, mean and standard deviation was used. The result of the analysis was presented in Table 1

Table 1: The administrative effectiveness level of principals in Edo State's public secondary schools

Items of principals’ administrative Effectiveness	Mean	Standard deviation	Level of Effectiveness
Curriculum coordination	2.57	1.01	Moderate
Instructional supervision	2.97	0.72	Moderate
Staff personnel function	2.67	0.80	Moderate
Student personnel function	3.16	0.73	High
Physical facilities maintenance	3.03	0.69	High
School community relations	3.06	0.74	High
Liaison functions	3.07	0.71	High
Routine office work	3.03	0.74	High
Timetable schedule compliance	2.83	0.76	Moderate
Involvement of others	3.23	0.95	High
School finance management	2.88	0.58	Moderate
Communication functions	3.38	0.53	High
Cluster mean	2.99	0.31	Moderate

KEY:

1 – 1.99: Low Effectiveness, 2 – 2.99: Moderate Effectiveness, 3 – 4.00: High Effectiveness

Table 1 shows the mean rating of principals' administrative effectiveness in Edo State public secondary schools, which range from 2.57 to 3.38. However, the mean ratings of 3.16, 3.03, 3.06, 3.07, 3.03, 3.23 and 3.38 standard deviations of 0.73, 0.69, 0.74, 0.71, 0.74, 0.95 and 0.53 respectively showed that the principals were rated high in administrative effectiveness in students’ personnel functions, physical facilities maintenance, school community relations, liaison function, routine office work, involvement of others and communication functions. However, they were rated moderately effectively in curriculum coordination, instructional supervision, staff personnel functions, time schedule compliance and school finance management. The cluster mean of 2.99 and standard deviation of 0.31 showed that principals' administrative effectiveness in Edo State public secondary schools was moderate.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between principals’ time management practices and administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Edo state.

To test this hypothesis, the Pearson r statistics were used to determine the relationship. The result of the analysis was presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Pearson r of the relationship between principals' time management practices and administrative effectiveness

	N	Pearson r	p-value
Time Management Practices	120	0.574	0.000

Level of Administrative Effectiveness

0.05 level of significance

Table 2 indicates a Pearson r value of 0.574 and a p-value of 0.000. The alpha level is greater than the p-value, when testing at an alpha level of 0.05. As a result, the null hypothesis that there is “no significant relationship between principals' time management practices and level of administrative effectiveness” is rejected. As a result, there is a significant relationship between principals' time management practices and their level of administrative effectiveness. The r square value of 0.3295 indicates that principals' time management practices accounted for approximately 33% of their administrative effectiveness.

Discussion of Results

The findings revealed that the level of principals' administrative effectiveness was moderate. The mean scores for twelve main administrative activities ranged from 2.57 to 3.38. However, the mean rating of 3.16, 3.03, 3.06, 3.07, 3.03, 3.23 and 3.38 standard deviations of 0.73, 0.69, 0.74, 0.71, 0.74, 0.95 and 0.53 respectively showed that the principals were rated high in administrative effectiveness in students' personnel functions, physical facilities maintenance, school community relations, liaison function, routine office work, involvement of others and communication functions. However, they were rated moderately effectively in curriculum coordination, instructional supervision, staff personnel functions, time schedule compliance and school finance management. This finding corroborated Ekundayo and Kolawole (2013) who found that the administrative effectiveness of principals was encouraging. The cluster mean of 2.99 and standard deviation of 0.31 shows that the level of administrative effectiveness of principals in Edo State public secondary schools was moderate" This finding aligns with Ogonor and Imarhiagbe (2007), who reported that teachers perceived principals as effective in managing instructional programs, student and staff personnel, instructional facility maintenance, and school-community relations."

Ekundayo and Kolawole (2013) found that teachers perceived the level of principals' administrative effectiveness as high. According to Ogonor and Imahiagbe (2007), amid the effective ranking of principals by teachers on administrative effectiveness in Edo state, the alleged fallen standard of secondary education has been blamed on the principals' failure to conduct school administrative functions effectively. The moderate level of administrative effectiveness may be attributed to principals' understanding and implementation of reasonable time management practices when fulfilling their duties in the school. It is assumed that the experience gathered over the years as teachers, heads of departments and vice principals would help them in this regard. Nevertheless, it is also assumed that the shortage of human and physical resources needed to enhance the principals' time management effectiveness towards creating conducive teaching learning environment may have contributed to their level of administrative effectiveness.

The results of the study revealed a positive significant relationship between principals' time management practices and administrative effectiveness, therefore corroborating the findings of Adebayo and Omojola (2012), who discovered a relationship between time management and administrative effectiveness. Kayode and Ayodele (2015) discovered a relationship between teachers' time management and students' academic achievement. The result is not surprising, given that good time management has

long been recognized as a key factor in achieving effectiveness in different fields and in life in general. This implies that effective time management is crucial for principals' effectiveness. It is an indication that principals have been able to prioritize their daily tasks and adopted appropriate time management practices and administrative styles that balanced tasks and relations to make the school environment conducive for the attainment of school goals.

The time management practices of principals indicate their priorities and the level of thoroughness and orderliness in the performance of their duties. Adoption of appropriate time management practices by the principals ensures that no aspect of their tasks is neglected or undermined in favour of another. Adoption of unprofessional practices could result in time wasting and consequently impinging on principals' effectiveness.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concluded that principals were found to be moderately effective in terms of administrative effectiveness. The study also showed a relationship between principals' time management practices and administrative effectiveness.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study to improve principals' administrative effectiveness.

1. Principals should not only plan their activities but also allocate time objectively according to priorities.
2. Regardless of school location, size, or level, the Ministry of Education should organize conferences, seminars, and workshops for principals to improve their time management skills.

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